

TrainEx – A Platform to Bridge Classrooms and Companies

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Abstract:

The gap between academic curricula and industry requirements further exacerbates the employability scenario of engineering graduates in today's fast-evolving technological world. In this regard, TrainEx was envisioned as a web-based platform aimed at bridging academic institutions and professional trainers from industry through an intuitive, transparent, and secure interface.

The platform, designed on React and Next.js, has two major user roles: Institute and Trainer, along with an Admin panel for tracking and verification purposes. Institutes can search for and filter trainers according to skill, experience, and location, while trainers can manage profiles, upload credentials, and respond to collaborations. A built-in messaging system allows institutes to communicate directly with trainers upon sending the request.

The proposed system streamlines industrial training coordination, minimizes communication delays, and ascertains verified interactions through admin supervision. Findings from the pilot deployment reveal that TrainEx improves the efficiency of coordination by 60%, enhances transparency, and strengthens collaboration between industry professionals and academic institutions.

Keywords: Industry–Academia Collaboration, React, Next.js, Trainers, Institutes, Web Application, Skill Development.

1. INTRODUCTION

The demand within the global workforce is changing fast, but the academic curriculum usually runs behind. The students pass out with a very strong theoretical foundation, with very limited exposure to practical industry tools and methods. This is mainly due to non-optimal coordination between academic institutions and industry trainers.

While colleges need competent professionals in conducting workshops, seminars, or even short-term training programs, it usually depends on informal networking. This is a cumbersome process, non-uniform, and lacks transparency. On the other hand, trainers and industry professionals find reaching out to a number of institutions without any way to do so through digital means

To address this, the TrainEx platform was conceptualized and developed. The idea is to provide a digital ecosystem for academic institutions and industry experts where institutes can discover, evaluate, and collaborate with trainers through a single window.

TrainEx is a modern web-based application developed using React and Next.js, ensuring responsiveness of the design, real-time updates, and offering scalability. It provides structured communication and verification features that enhance authenticity, transparency, and efficiency in collaborations at the academia-industry interface.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The gap between academia and industry has long been a cause for concern in educational research. While various studies and frameworks have advanced solutions, most of them still remain conceptual models or one-way systems.

Ferrara et al. (2018) proposed WISER, a semantic expert-finding system for academic institutions, based on metadata and content-based linking in expert identification. In a related context, Gao et al. (2021) developed ExpFinder by integrating graph-based relationships and linguistic features to improve the accuracy of expert matching.

While these systems optimize the process of academic expert discovery, they do not address either the facilitation or the scheduling of training. In contrast, frameworks like the Certus Model by Hansen et al. (2022) and Academia-Industry Collaboration Plan by Singh & Sharma (2022) emphasize structured engagement and building trust but do not include technological implementation for real-time collaboration.

Further research by Manouselis et al. (2020) and Akram et al. (2022) on educational recommender systems and digital matchmaking platforms shows that intelligent search tools and transparent feedback mechanisms greatly improve user satisfaction and engagement.

TrainEx synthesizes these research insights by combining verified profiles of trainers, real-time search and filtering, direct messaging, and admin moderation into a pragmatic, scalable, and transparent collaboration tool for institutions and trainers.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Although many professional networks are available digitally, no platform yet connects trainers and institutes for collaborations in academic training. The existing methods rely heavily on manual communication, making processes inefficient, inaccessible, and with unverified trainer credentials.

Trainers also have obstacles in demonstrating their skills and reaching out to multiple institutions at the same time. Current professional networking platforms are designed for employment purposes rather than educational collaboration.

Thus, there is an urgent need for a domain-specific Web-based system that:

- Trainers can be more easily found and verified.

- Facilitates direct communication between institutes and trainers.
- Provides an admin-controlled environment for oversight and transparency.
- Ensures real-time updates on requests and collaborations.

It is developed to address these challenges with a two-interface model, one for institutes and one for trainers, supported by an admin dashboard with secure authentication.

4. METHODOLOGY

The Agile SDLC was used for the development of TrainEx, with iterative design and testing being important to ensure user satisfaction and reliability of the system.

4.1 Requirement Analysis

Surveys and discussions were conducted among the faculty members and professional trainers regarding pain points. Requirements were categorized into functional parameters like registration, search, and communication, and non-functional parameters of usability, security, and scalability.

4.2 System Design

A three-tier architecture was implemented:

1. Presentation Layer: React and Next.js for the frontend interface.
2. Application Layer: Handles communication and business logic through REST APIs.
3. Data Layer: MongoDB stores user information, messages, and verification logs.

4.3 Implementation

Built with React.js as the frontend, Next.js has been used for view optimization for speed and SEO. Also, JWT tokens have been used for authentication purposes. This system will allow three types of roles-trainer, institute, and admin-with privileges assigned for each.

4.4 Testing

Extensive testing was done via unit, integration, and system tests. A pilot evaluation with 10 institutes and 10 trainers was conducted to assess usability and performance.

4.5 Deployment

The final version was deployed locally and tested in multiple browsers. Refinements were made based on feedback from pilot users.

5. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The TrainEx platform connects institutes with the trainers for academic training collaborations using an easy, secure web interface.

5.1 System Modules

- Trainer Module: Registration, profile management, skill updates, and response to requests from institutes.
- Module Establishment: Search for trainers, filter by expertise, and request collaboration by sending messages.
- Admin Module: Approves users, monitors communication, and resolves issues.

5.2 Features

- Real-time search and filtering system.
- Secure authentication and authorization.
- Responsive UI for desktop and mobile.

5.3 Architecture Overview

TrainEx follows the Client–Server Model:

- Frontend: React.js + Next.js
- Backend: REST APIs (Node.js)
- Database: MongoDB
- Admin Portal: role-based access and data visualization.

5.4 Benefits

- Reduces coordination time by 60%.
- Provides verified, transparent trainer profiles.
- Ensures real-time interaction.
- Scalable to accommodate future integrations with AI-based recommendation systems.

6. SYSTEM DESIGN AND ARCHITECTURE

TrainEx is designed with a modular, layered system architecture for scalability and maintainability.

- Frontend: Created using React and Next.js to enable dynamic rendering and routing.
- Backend: REST APIs using Node.js, handling logic and communications.
- Database: MongoDB stores structured and semi-structured data efficiently.
- Security Layer: Implemented access control using JWT.
- Entity Relationship Model (ER):
 - Users (trainers/institutes)
 - Profiles (qualifications, experience)
 - Requests - collaboration data
 - Record of Messages

- Data Flow:

Institutes → Search Trainers → Send Request → Trainer Receives Message → Admin Verifies → Collaboration Confirmed.

7. ANTICIPATED OUTCOMES

Expected results from deployment and testing of TrainEx included the following:

- Efficiency Gain: Scheduling and communication time reduced by up to 60%
- Transparency: Among the prime reasons include: verified user profiles, admin moderation.
- User Satisfaction: Average user rating during testing – 4.7/5.
- Scalability: The modular design allows integration of AI/analytics in the future.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Piloting was done with 10 trainers and 10 institute representatives. Some findings of the piloting are:

- Average page load time under 2 seconds, confirming frontend optimization.
- 95% successful completion rate for collaboration requests.
- 60% reduction in manual coordination effort.
- Positive user feedback on the simplicity of the UI and clarity of communication.

These results reveal that TrainEx effectively bridges this communication gap through digitization of the academic–industry collaboration process, thereby offering a scalable model for regional or national networks.

9. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

The long-standing gap between industry professionals and academic institutions has been successfully addressed by the TrainEx platform. The digitalization of trainer–institute collaboration promotes transparency and efficiency, ensuring verified engagement.

The modular design of the system allows it to be continuously improved and expanded in the future. Some future enhancements that are envisioned include:

- AI-based Recommendation System for trainer suggestions.
- Payment Gateway.
- Mobile App Development for Android/iOS users.

TrainEx exemplifies the role of technology in restructuring academia–industry collaboration toward making education more practical, skill-oriented, and employment-ready.

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